

STEMIFY

Modules

Project number NPHZ-2023/10068

2025

STEMIFY Modules

STEMify Your Classroom: STEM Platforms for Quality Education

Teachers and teacher trainers in different educational sectors (on the one hand, school, vocational, higher and adult; and, on the other hand, formal, non-formal and informal) are the target group of this handbook.

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Executive Summary

These Modules aim to support teachers and teacher trainers in different educational sectors (on the one hand, school, vocational, higher and adult; and, on the other hand, formal, non-formal and informal) with teaching tools in their work with learners including disadvantaged ones for the improvement of their skills in STEM for green, competitive and socially sustainable future.

Project Background and Context

During 2023-2025, Centre for Education and Innovation Research from Riga Latvia implemented the Nordplus Horizontal Project “STEMify Your Classroom: STEM Platforms for Quality Education”, Project number NPHZ-2023/10068. The partners of the STEMIFY project are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: STEMIFY Partner Institutions

	<p>Institution: Centre for Education and Innovation Research City: Riga Country: Latvia</p>
	<p>Institution: University the Faroe Islands City: Tórshavn Country: the Faroe Islands</p>
	<p>Institution: Be-Creative Association Town: Kristianstad Country: Sweden</p>
	<p>Institution: Learnmera Town: Espoo Country: Finland</p>

	<p>Institution: Island Panorama Center City: Reykjavik Country: Iceland</p>
	<p>Institution: Exclusive Style City: Riga Country: Latvia</p>
	<p>Institution: Center for job and education City: Nuuk Country: Greenland</p>

Socially sustainable future stems from green and competitive economy. STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) is the driver for making Europe economy green and competitive and, therefore, increasing social sustainability. Due to this, STEM attracts more and more attention at all the educational levels. STEM education is known as the combination of four disciplines - Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, (Ahrens, Emet, Zascerska, Jõesalu, Rohdin, Olsson, Gelfgren, Opongo, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerskis, Abjalkiene, Glonina, & Gukovica, 2024) as depicted in Figure 1.

STEM education fosters technological development that, in turn, impacts economic growth and, therefore, human well-being.

STEM education is also the driver for making Europe climate neutral for our greener future and protecting our natural habitat (Zascerska, Emet, Usca, & Bikova, 2023).

Figure 1: STEM Disciplines

The aim of the intended project is to establish new course modules using STEM Platforms in different educational sectors (on the one hand, school, public, private, enterprise, adult, and language education; and, on the other hand, formal, non-formal and informal) and support teachers with teaching modules in their work with learners including disadvantaged ones aimed at improving their learners' skills in in STEM for green, competitive and socially sustainable future, thereby increasing their learners' educational and social inclusion and promoting social sustainability.

Chapter 1

Module Background and Scope

Module Background and Scope

STEM modules aim to promote learners' skills in these four disciplines - Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, (Ahrens, Emet, Zascerinska, Jõesalu, Rohdin, Olsson, Gelfgren, Opongo, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, Abjalkiene, Glonina, & Gukovica, 2024). These skills include

- Problem-solving,
- Innovation,
- Data analytics,
- Digital tools,
- Academic writing,
- Ethics,
- Material design,
- Resource management,
- Mathematica software
- Mathematical methods of statistics.

This list is not exhaustive.

These skills are crucial to succeed in STEM education and life. Learners with enriched STEM skills are able to perform in a sustainable manner in their education and wider life. Sustainable approach to STEM education let learners to balance their performance when solving a problem and looking for an innovative solution. Sustainable approach to STEM education links and explains life scenarios and their results.

STEM skills help learners become efficient problem solvers and also facilitates the creation of better learning opportunities focused on social integration.

Emotional cognition as teaching methodology in STEM education is found to be relevant as there is the shift in the emotions' status from a psychological phenomenon to the educational category (Ahrens, Zascerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023b). The inter-connections between emotions and cognition play the key role in education (Ahrens, Zascerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023b). Emotional engagement of an individual or a group into STEM platform modules is highly important as any kind of education is driven by emotions (Ahrens, Zascerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023c). It should be noted that emotions are primary in comparison to cognition (Ahrens, Zascerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023c). Therefore, STEM modules should be first attractive and, then, qualitative.

Emotions are the driver of the educational process (Ahrens, Zascerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023c). During the educational process, emotional skills are processed via cognitive evaluation, and, therefore emotional skills are converted into the cognitive output/outcome/result (Ahrens, Zascerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023b) as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Phases of emotional cognition in the educational process

Main Subject

The four STEM modules aim at stabilising learners' emotional and cognitive involvement in STEM education and their results crucial for the enrichment of learners' skills as well as learners' wider environment and life.

Table 2 reveals the four STEM modules and key topics in each relevant module.

Table 2: Four STEM modules and their key topics

Module	Key topics
Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Sustainable Development in the globalised world,- Links between science, research, and study,- Ethics issues in science, and- Health and safety in working environments
Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Problem Solving,- Innovation,- Use of STEM platforms, and- Artificial Intelligence (AI) in academic writing
Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Sustainable and green engineering,- Material science,- Resource management, and- Innovative engineer biography
Mathematics	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Data science and simulation,- Learning analytics,- Mathematical methods of statistics, and

	- Mathematical software
--	-------------------------

Teaching each module and each topic is based on interdisciplinary approach. By interdisciplinary approach, shared aim oriented joint activity or, in other words, process according to certain common norms, over some period of time that provides knowledge variety through joint social interaction and cognitive activity and increases opportunities of creating new knowledge (Zaščerinska, Ahrens, & Bassus, 2015) is meant.

Each module, namely Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics, offers training materials to teachers and teacher trainers.

Each module is built on the development of STEM skills reflected in Table 3.

Table 3: Four STEM modules, their key topics and skills

Module	Key topics	Skills
Science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable Development in the globalised world, - Links between science, research, and study, - Ethics issues in science, and - Health and safety in working environments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Critical thinking - Analytical thinking - Scientific inquiry - Collaboration - Communication - Adaptability - Lifelong learning
Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Problem Solving, - Innovation, - Use of STEM platforms, and - Artificial Intelligence (AI) in academic writing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Problem solving - Creativity - Innovation - Digital skills - Writing skills

Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable and green engineering, - Material science, - Resource management, and - Innovative engineer biography 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Project management - Team work - Design thinking - Role model - Leadership
Mathematics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data science and simulation, - Learning analytics, - Mathematical methods of statistics, and - Mathematical software 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data literacy - Analytical reasoning - Mathematical skills - Critical thinking - Technological literacy

The four Modules proposes the use of teaching methods such as

- Workplace learning,
- Project based learning,
- Inquiry based learning,
- Group discussions,
- Solving problem situations, and
- Context analysis.

The Module delivery will require the following resources:

- Worksheets,
- Group discussion,
- Multiple choices,
- Text input.

Each Module duration is 4 hours in total:

- 3 hours of group study, and
- 1 hour of independent work of learners.

Target Group

The target group of these modules is teachers and teacher trainers in different educational sectors:

- on the one hand, school, vocational, higher and adult; and,
- on the other hand, formal, non-formal and informal.

The secondary target group is learners belonging to different educational levels.

These STEM modules can be also used by such learners if they feel that teacher's help is not necessary for them.

Chapter 2

Teaching Module in Science

Module Aim

The overall aim of the Module is to enhance teachers' and teacher trainers' teaching practice focused on the development of science skills of STEM learners.

The enabling objectives are:

1. To develop teachers' and teacher trainers' knowledge about science skills:

- Sustainable approach to science,
- Links between science, research, and study,
- Ethical issues in science
- Health and safety in working environments.

2. To update teachers' and teacher trainers' skills to organise a relevant and appropriate teaching practice with the use of tools for the measurement of science skills of STEM learners

3. To increase teachers' and teacher trainers' attitude to teaching practices focused on the development of science skills of STEM learners.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of the Module, teachers' and teacher trainers' will be able to

- Identify science skills,
- Navigate through science skills and learning to learn,
- Use their science skills in practice:
 - Self-evaluate their science awareness
 - Identify links between science, research, and study
 - Solve ethical dilemmas in science
 - Self-evaluate their health and safety in working environments
- Apply emotional cognition method for the development of science skills of STEM learners
- To increase the attitude of learners to the development of their science skills.

Tools for Science Module

Tool 1: Sustainable Development

1.1. Please, discuss the links between globalisation in the world and sustainable development:

Sustainability is a response to the global pressing issue of the human impact on the environment (Griswold, 2016) and the Earth planet. Sustainability practice creates the tension between maintaining the status quo and changing our existing structures and relationships (Griswold, 2016).

1.2. Please, discuss the changing concept of sustainability illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4: Changes in the concept of sustainability (Ahrens, Dzerviniks, Skromule, Usca, Blazulioniene, Zascerska, Kavolius, & Hognadottir, 2024)

Sustainability concept		
	20 th Century	21 st Century
Notion	Sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present generation without compromising the chances of future generations to	Sustainability means prioritising the needs of all life forms and of the planet by ensuring that human activity does not exceed

	meet their own needs and aspirations (United Nations, 1987).	planetary boundaries (Bianchi, Pisiotis, & Cabrera Giraldez, 2022).
Procedures	Three types of approaches (United Nations, 1987): -Economic, -Social, -Environmental.	Nine Earth system processes (Bianchi, Pisiotis, & Cabrera Giraldez, 2022): 1) biosphere integrity, 2) land-use change, 3) climate change, 4) freshwater use, 5) ocean acidification, 6) biogeochemical flows (nitrogen and phosphorus cycles), 7) atmospheric aerosol pollution, 8) stratospheric ozone depletion, 9) release of novel chemicals.

1.3. Please, evaluate your sustainability competences paying attention to each element of sustainability competence indicated in Table 5.

Table 5: Sustainability competence (adapted from Bianchi, Pisiotis, & Cabrera Giraldez, 2022)

Sustainability competence		
<i>Valuing sustainability</i>	<i>Supporting fairness</i>	<i>Promoting nature</i>

Personal values	Equity	Natural environment (geosphere, biosphere, hydrosphere, cryosphere and atmosphere)
	Justice	Other species
		Healthy and resilient ecosystems

Tool 2: Science, Research, and Study

2.1. Please, define what science, research, and study are taking into consideration that

Science is well-recognized to be the driver of moving the world to a better future for all (Ahrens, Zascerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023b).

Science and research (the basis of science) are aimed at solving the dilemma of cause, on the one side, and effect, also known as change, on the other side (Ahrens, Zascerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023b).

Science means the knowledge about the world: the notion structure and processes of different world's phenomena (Ahrens, Zaščerinska, Bikova, Aleksejeva, Zascerinskis, & Gukovica, 2023a). Research is a means of broadening scientific knowledge about the world. Research is the process (Ahrens & Zascerinska, 2015). Study means a detailed investigation and analysis of a subject or a situation (Oxford Dictionary, 2025).

2.2. Please, answer the question: Why do we do a research? Figure 3 can help you find some reasons for doing research.

Figure 3: Research aims

2.3. Quiz: please, choose a correct answer in each question:

1. What is academic research?

- a) A process of gathering information for personal knowledge only
- b) A systematic investigation into a specific topic or issue to discover new information or validate existing knowledge
- c) A casual exploration of ideas without any structured approach

2. What is academic writing?

- a) Any form of writing done by scholars for personal use
- b) Writing that follows specific conventions and standards for scholarly communication
- c) Informal writing with no citation or reference requirements

3. Which of the following is NOT a characteristic of academic writing?

- a) Clarity and precision
- b) Use of jargon to impress the readers
- c) Formal tone and language

4. What is the primary goal of academic research?

- a) To entertain readers with interesting facts
- b) To persuade readers to adopt a particular viewpoint

c) To contribute new knowledge to a field of study

Tool 3: Ethics in science

3.1. Could you explain what ethics is. Please, refer to Table 6 to compare ethics, morals, and law.

Table 6: Ethics, morals and law

Ethics	Morals	Law
It is a process of reflection in which peoples' decisions are shaped by their values, principles, and purposes rather than unthinking habits, social conventions, or self-interest. Can be clear guidelines and dictate how one should behave and help shape law and regulations that reflect them	Informal framework of values, principles, beliefs, and norms, customs, ways of living, that can even act as "societal pressure to follow"	Clear (sometimes not that clear codes of conduct or guidelines that have consequences if not followed)

3.2. Please, discuss the situations when your scientific knowledge can be shared with others and when it is worth to hold it as illustrated in Figure 4 (Aaron, 2015).

Figure 4: Ethical dilemma in science (Aaron, 2015)

3.3. Please discuss your choice of a patient who should get an artificial lung ventilation device in the COVID-19 Pandemic Dilemma.

Latvia: Two dying patients and one artificial lung ventilation device (Latvijas Sabiedriskais medijs, 2020) as illustrated in Figure 5.

In the event of an acute shortage of resources, patients are divided into groups conditionally by color:

- **Blue** group - patients have a high mortality prognosis. They are not intubated. Artificial lung ventilation is not performed. Adequate palliative care is provided.
- **Red** group - patients have a deficiency of one organ (for example, pneumonia). They need to be provided with maximum treatment, as the potential for recovery is high.

- **Yellow** group - patients with multiple diseases, with a stable degree of compensation of pathology. Intensive therapy and artificial ventilation of the lungs are provided to them, if there are no applicants from the red group.
- **Green** group - patients will survive without mechanical ventilation.

Figure 5: Artificial lung ventilation device (Latvijas Sabiedriskais medijs, 2020)

Tool 4: Health and safety in working environments

4.1. Do you follow health and safety regulations and rules in your working environment. Please, explain why.

4.2. Who is responsible for your health and safety regulations in working environment? Please, explain why.

4.3. Please, take part in the Quiz (Link to Sexual Harassment In Workplace Quiz: <https://saynotogenderdiscrimination.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Questionnaire-and-levels-of-exposure-EN.pdf>):

Questions and Answers:

1. Sexual Harassment is _____ sexual advances, requests for sexual favors, and/or other verbal, visual, or physical conduct of a sexual nature.

- A. Unwarrented
- B. Obvious
- C. Unwelcome
- D. All of the above

2. If your intentions are good, your behavior cannot be considered sexual harassment.

- A. True
- B. False

3. If you ignore the behavior of sexual harassment, it will ultimately stop or go away.

- A. True
- B. False

4. Sexual harassment may include actions by members of

- A. Opposite genders.
- B. Same gender.
- C. Both the opposite and same gender.
- D. None of the above

5. Sexual harassment can occur outside the work site and still be considered work related. Incidents that occur at retirement parties and office socials or in training are some of the situations where work related harassment occurs.

- A. True
- B. False

6. Sexual harassment is not limited to physical contact. It can occur any time that an individual is _____ another person's approaches, comments, or discussions.

- A. Avoiding
- B. Uncomfortable with
- C. Irritated by
- D. All of the above

7. Dirty jokes and language may be construed as sexual harassment.

- A. True
- B. False

8. A man who is sexually harassed does not have the same legal rights as a woman who is sexually harassed.

- A. True
- B. False

9. Quid Pro Quo harassment is a form of sexual harassment when there is a request or demand of sexual favors in exchange for employment benefits or threatening retaliation if the favors are not given.

- A. True
- B. False

10. An employee witnesses another employee being harassed. Even though this involved a co-worker, the witness can be considered _____ in this case.

- A. A victim
- B. An accomplice
- C. Uninvolved
- D. All of the above

11. Altius policy _____ sexual harassment.

- A. Is lenient with
- B. Prohibits
- C. Allows explanations for
- D. All of the above

12. Employees who encounter harassment, directly or indirectly, have a responsibility to take advantage of the provided resources and procedures to protect themselves from unlawful harassment.

- A. True
- B. False

13. Incidents of harassment are made public within the organization to keep employees informed.

- A. True
- B. False

14. All employees share responsibility for ensuring that the workplace is free from sexual harassment.

- A. True
- B. False

15. Employees can make a good faith report to their supervisor, the Director of Human Resources, or a senior company leader without fear of discipline or retaliation.

- A. True
- B. False

Chapter 3

Teaching Module in Technology

Module Aim

The overall aim of the Module is to enhance teachers' and teacher trainers' teaching practice focused on the development of technology skills of STEM learners.

The enabling objectives are:

1. To develop teachers' and teacher trainers' knowledge about technology skills:
 - Problem-solving,
 - Innovation,
 - Use of STEM Platforms
 - Artificial Intelligence (AI) in academic writing.
2. To update teachers' and teacher trainers' skills to organise a relevant and appropriate teaching practice with the use of tools for the measurement of technology skills of STEM learners
3. To increase teachers' and teacher trainers' attitude to teaching practices focused on the development of technology skills of STEM learners.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of the Module, teachers' and teacher trainers' will be able to

- Identify technology skills,
- Navigate through technology skills and learning to learn,
- Use their technology skills in practice:
 - Search for a solution of problem-solving
 - Use of design tools for innovation visualisation
 - Use of STEM platforms
 - Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in academic writing
- Apply emotional cognition method for the development of technology skills of STEM learners
- To increase the attitude of learners to the development of their technology skills.

Tools for Technology Module

Tool 1: Problem Solving

1.1. Please, define what problem and problem situation are.

Problem is a contraction. Contradiction means two incompatible requirements set to one phenomenon or element / subject/ etc.

Figure 6 shows the definition of problem from the external and internal perspectives.

External perspective	Internal perspective
Challenge and opportunity	Gain and possibility
The system of the external and internal perspectives	

Figure 6: The definition of the term “problem” from the external and internal perspectives (Zaščerinska, Aleksejeva, Zaščerinskis, Gukovica, & Aleksejeva, 2021)

1.2. What is problem solving?

Problem solving means to turn a challenge or opportunity into a gain and possibility (Zaščerinska, Aleksejeva, Zaščerinskis, Gukovica, & Aleksejeva, 2021).

- 1.3. Please, read the text “Problem Solving” (De Bono, 1994) and answer the questions: Question 1 – how many methods of problem solving are presented? Question 2 – Please, describe each method.

Most of the major problems in the world today persist precisely because we have such an excellent method of problem-solving. This statement is not intended to be sarcastic. We do have an excellent method of problem-solving. It is so good, however, that we have come to believe that it will solve all problems. So we have not bothered to develop any other method. The good is often the enemy of the best. If something is very good then we stop there and cloak ourselves in complacency.

What is this excellent, traditional, method of problem-solving? It is yet another example of the basic belief that if you 'remove the bad things' you will be left with the good things.

So the general method is that you analyse the problem, identify the cause and then proceed to remove the cause. The cause of the problem is removed so the problem is solved. It works. If you have a sore throat you identify the bacteria as a streptococcus. You take penicillin to kill the streptococcus. You have removed the cause and you get better. You feel a sharp pain when you sit down on a chair. You examine the cushion and find a pin. You remove the pin and the problem is solved. You analyse the problem of inflation and find that it is caused by excess money supply and too high a velocity of circulation of money. So you remove the cause by making money more expensive with high interest rates. You have cured inflation. You may, of course, also have caused a recession by driving out of business many small operations that cannot survive the high interest rates, but that does not matter.

The general method is simple and it works well, when it works. But there are some problems where you cannot find the cause. There are other problems where there are so many causes that you cannot remove all of them. Then there are problems where you can find the cause but you cannot remove it. Perhaps you cannot remove the cause because it is human nature, and you cannot easily remove that.

What do we do in such cases? We just try harder. We try harder with yet more analysis. We try harder to remove the cause. A classic example is the drug problem. We try harder to remove the cause. While acknowledging the excellence of the general method of solving a problem by identifying and removing the cause, we also need to do something about those instances where the method simply does not work. Are these insoluble problems? Possibly, but we ought at least to try some other methods.

Given our technical competence, how much further ahead would we have been with a more constructive thinking style?

An alternative method is to leave the cause in place and to 'design' a way forward. We do not like doing this. There are two reasons for this dislike. The first is a rather 'purist' reason. We believe that if the cause is still in place then our solution is just papering over the cracks and is only cosmetic. It is as if the cause is a sort of 'untruth' which cannot be tolerated. The second reason is that designing the way forward requires new concepts and creativity. This is difficult, and we do not like creativity because we prefer to feel that analysis is sufficient. The whole thrust of education is towards analysis. Everything should yield to analysis in our traditional methods of thinking. Very little emphasis is given to creativity.

We apply the general idiom of 'remove the bad' to many situations. Our intellectuals are trained to be 'against things'. It is enough to be against

pollution. It is enough to be against racial discrimination. In some cases it is indeed enough. Values do change. People do feel guilty about smoking. Bad things do

get curbed or even removed. The idiom does have its place.

Being against things is not enough. We also need to develop the habits of constructive thinking.

My point is that being against things is not enough. We also need to develop the habits of constructive thinking. But we do not. Educated people are well trained to be against things but poorly trained to be constructive. Being constructive is for artists or those materialistic people who want to make money in business. This is all part of the traditional thinking system that really does believe that analysis and argument are enough. Given our technical competence, how much further ahead would we have been with a more constructive thinking style?

We naively believe that the good things (like truth) are already there, obscured by bad things or hidden from sight. Search is enough. Being constructive is irrelevant. All that comes from the traditional thinking system set up by the Gang of Three. Should we not move on?

Tool 2: Innovation

2.1. Please, read the text "Information vs Idea" (De Bono, 1994) and find definitions of what information and idea are. What is the difference between information and idea?

Thinking is no substitute for information. Information is essential. Information has a high value. Information is a 'good thing'.

Since information is good, more information is even better. There are people who believe that if you get enough information then the information will do your thinking for you. Many people in business believe that. Of course, if information really could make the decisions then we should not need people, because information in a computer would flow along to give the decision output. This may happen in the future. For the moment, the human being is a sort of junction who adds to the information, ideas, values and politics and then passes on to a decision. In the past, information was the real bottleneck, so any improvement in information would lead to an improvement in thinking and in the quality of decisions. Information access and handling (by computers) have widened that bottleneck. So we move on to the next bottleneck. This is 'thinking'. What do we do with the information? Most people in business and government have not fully faced that change.

If information is good, more information is better. This follows directly from the traditional thinking system. <...>

There are times when too much information clutters up the system, obscures what is really important, and reduces flexibility. If you have to go into the most minute details of every person you interview then the process is going to take so long that you are only able to interview a few people.

We love information because it is unquestionably valuable and it is easy to deal with - especially today. Education loves information. There was a time when it was possible for education to give a student virtually all the known scientific knowledge. The attitude of accumulating all possible information has persisted even though it is, today, total nonsense to try to do so.

There is, however, a dilemma. Everyone knows that a little bit more of information is very valuable. So where do we draw the line and say that it is not practical to teach more information? Where do we draw the line in order to say

that we should spend time on teaching thinking skills rather than on teaching more information? It is not at all easy - which is why it is not happening.

It is the concept through which we perceive the information that gives it any value.

Information is easy to handle. There are books and libraries. You can put a book before a student and keep the student busy that way. The sheer mechanics of information are practical and attractive.

Ideas are a different matter. How do we produce ideas on demand? We can read about other people's ideas, but that is information. We may believe that ideas are a sort of divine inspiration over which we have no control. That is an old-fashioned view. We can design and produce ideas as easily as we can produce information -or even more easily. The deliberate and formal techniques of lateral thinking can do this and are currently being taught in some schools and colleges. There is no mystery about the processes.

Many people still believe that analysis of information will, itself, create new ideas. This is not so, since the brain can only see what it is prepared to see. The analysis of information will allow us to select an idea from our repertoire of standard ideas but not to find a new idea. To 'see' a new idea we have first to imagine or speculate, so that the idea has a brief existence in our mind. Then we may be able to see the idea in the information. <...>

The analysis of information will allow us to select an idea from our repertoire of standard ideas but not to find a new idea. Analysis of the sales of life insurance might suggest that single people are not heavy buyers. Why should they be? They have no families that might be affected by their sudden death. So the insurance company sees no market in single people. The analysis of information has shown 'what is' in the usual way. But if the concept of life insurance is changed to include the 'living-needs benefits', then, suddenly, life insurance is very attractive to

single people because it also becomes catastrophic-illness insurance. The new concept is that if the insured person gets a serious illness which might be fatal then the insurance company will immediately pay out 75 per cent of the benefits which would otherwise be payable only on death. This money can be used for medical care.

The mathematical analysis of queues has been well worked out in operations research. It is possible to work out the waiting time, the number of serving positions needed etc. But analysis of this sort is not going to lead to the new idea of having an extra serving position indicating that if you want to be served at that position then you pay a small fee. If too many people use that position the fee is raised. The money collected goes to open a further serving position, so benefiting everyone else as well. In this way someone in a hurry can set a value on his or her waiting time.

Ideas are organizing structures which put values and information together in new ways. Ideas need creative effort. Just collecting more information or analysing it more thoroughly will not produce ideas. This seems so obvious, and yet the bulk of our activity is spent on those activities and not on the generation of ideas. It could be that we do not see the value of ideas. This is hard to believe. It could be that we hope that analysis and more information will produce the needed ideas. Both experience and a simple understanding of the nature of self-organizing information systems will tell us that this is unlikely to be sufficient. We may believe that only chance and genius can produce ideas and there is nothing we can do about it. I suspect that this last belief is responsible for our lack of attention to serious creativity. <...>

There is a further point which needs mentioning. Universities only really got going at about the time of the Renaissance, although many had existed before. It was the Renaissance that opened up universities to new and secular thinking.

Before that they had been largely concerned with theology and scripture. At the Renaissance it was obvious to everyone that the best ideas were going to be obtained by looking backwards at what had been done by the Greek thinkers and the Roman doers. So it was a unique period in history when looking backwards was indeed more progressive than looking forwards. This practice has continued to this day and is dignified by the name of 'scholarship'. Work is valued mainly in terms of how competently it looks backwards and rarely on how well it might affect the future. We esteem the value of collection more than we esteem the value of concepts. The nonsense of this will be shown in the future when computer programs will be able to look through the literature, pick out all relevant papers, and then extract from them (through theme search) all relevant paragraphs and put these together as a scholarly work. The library function which is the basis of so much university work will then be taken over by computers. People should then be freed to think.

2.2. Please, think of new idea generation. How do you do it?

2.3. Design thinking includes 5 steps as shown in Figure 7. Please, describe each step in the process of innovation. Which step would you start with?, Explain your choice.

Figure 7. Five steps of design thinking (Uxcel, 2025)

Tool 3: Use os STEM Platforms

3.1. Please, give 3-5 names of STEM Platforms you use in your STEM learning?

3.2. Please, describe your experience with STEM Platforms: Did you like it? How often did you use STEM Platform? Were they user friendly?

3.3. What are the benefits of STEM Platforms? Please, give 5 reasons to use STEM Platforms.

Tool 4: Articial Intelligence in Academic Writing

4.1. Do you use Artificial Intelligence (AI) for your writing? Could you, please, explain your choice?

4.2. Could you, please explain ethical issues related to the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in academic writing taking into consideration that

It is important to acknowledge any sources or references used in the article to avoid plagiarism (Švab, Klemenc-Ketiš, Zupanič, 2023)

Nonhuman AI and language models are not legible for authorship (Levy, 2025) as they

- *Lack the ability to*
 - *Assume responsibility for the submitted work and*
 - *Approve copyright, and*
- *Cannot*
 - *Confirm conflicts of interest or*
 - *Manage copyright and*
 - *Manage licensing agreements required by authors.*

4.3. Please, discuss the benefits and drawback of using Artificial Intelligence (AI) in science as demonstrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The main benefits and drawbacks of AI in research (Bahammam, Trabelsi, Pandi-Perumal, & Jahrami, 2023)

Chapter 4

Teaching Module in Engineering

Module Aim

The overall aim of the Module is to enhance teachers' and teacher trainers' teaching practice focused on the development of engineering skills of STEM learners.

The enabling objectives are:

1. To develop teachers' and teacher trainers' knowledge about engineering skills:
 - Sustainable and green engineering,
 - Material Science,
 - Resource management
 - Engineer role model.
2. To update teachers' and teacher trainers' skills to organise a relevant and appropriate teaching practice with the use of tools for the measurement of engineering skills of STEM learners
3. To increase teachers' and teacher trainers' attitude to teaching practices focused on the development of engineering skills of STEM learners.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of the Module, teachers' and teacher trainers' will be able to

- Identify engineering skills,
- Navigate through engineering skills and learning to learn,
- Use their engineering skills in practice:
 - Application of sustainable and green engineering
 - Use of material science in engineering
 - Use of resource management in engineering
 - Use of role models
- Apply emotional cognition method for the development of engineering skills of STEM learners
- To increase the attitude of learners to the development of their engineering skills.

Tools for Engineering Module

Tool 1: Sustainable and green engineering

- 1.1. Please, define the importance of sustainable and green engineering.
- 1.2. What are green aspects in engineering?
- 1.3. Please, explain how green engineering impacts sustainable development.

Tool 2: Material science

- 2.1. Please, explain why materials science is important for engineering?
- 2.2. What kind of materials, e.g. metal, glass, wood, plastic, etc are you familiar with? Please describe characteristics of these materials.
- 2.3. Please, explain the relationship between material recycling and sustainability.

Tool 3: Resource Management

3.1. Please, define the inter-connections between resource management and sustainability?

3.2. Please, describe your experience in resource management: What kind of resources (financial, materials, equipment, human resources, etc) do you consider? What is your approach to resource management?

3.3. What are the benefits of resource management? Please, give 5 reasons to plan resource management.

Tool 4: Use of Role Models

4.1. Who are role models? Please, explain. Is there any difference between role model and influencer?

4.2. How engineer role models impact STEM education?

4.3. Please, give a short presentation about a successful engineer. Please, focus on

- his/her biography facts,
- inventions, and
- impact on engineering development.

Chapter 5

Teaching Module in Mathematics

Module Aim

The overall aim of the Module is to enhance teachers' and teacher trainers' teaching practice focused on the development of mathematics skills of STEM learners.

The enabling objectives are:

1. To develop teachers' and teacher trainers' knowledge about mathematics skills:
 - Data science and simulation,
 - Learning analytics,
 - Mathematical methods of Statistics,
 - Mathematical software.
2. To update teachers' and teacher trainers' skills to organise a relevant and appropriate teaching practice with the use of tools for the measurement of mathematical skills of STEM learners
3. To increase teachers' and teacher trainers' attitude to teaching practices focused on the development of mathematical skills of STEM learners.

Learning Outcomes

By the end of the Module, teachers' and teacher trainers' will be able to

- Identify mathematical skills,
- Navigate through mathematical skills and learning to learn,
- Use their mathematical skills in practice:
 - Application of data science and simulation
 - Use of learning analytics
 - Mathematical methods of statistics
 - Mathematical software
- Apply emotional cognition method for the development of mathematical skills of STEM learners
- To increase the attitude of learners to the development of their mathematical skills.

Tools for Mathematical Module

Tool 1: Data science and simulation

- 1.1. Please, define the importance of mathematics in data science.
- 1.2. What are the connections between mathematics, data science, and simulation?
- 1.3. Please, take quiz! Developed by (Stedman, Joyce, & Lavery, 2022).

Question 1 of 10

Which of the following best describes the principal goal of data science?

- To collect and archive exhaustive data sets from various source systems for corporate record keeping uses.
- To mine and analyze large amounts of data in order to uncover information that can be used for operational improvements and business gains.
- To collect and prepare data for use as part of analytics applications.

Question 2 of 10

What is the first step in the data science process?

- Collecting data and preparing it for analysis
- Experimenting with and tuning different analytical models
- Defining an analytical hypothesis that could provide business value

Question 3 of 10

What is the primary difference between a data scientist and a data engineer?

- A data engineer collects and prepares data, and a data scientist then analyzes it.
- A data engineer analyzes data after a data scientist collects and prepares it.
- A data engineer builds data pipelines and helps prepare data, while a data scientist is responsible for data collection, preparation and analysis.

Question 4 of 10

True or false? Data scientists typically need a combination of technical skills, nontechnical ones and suitable personality traits to be successful.

- True
- False

Question 5 of 10

Which of the following programming languages are most widely used by data scientists?

- C and C++
- Python, R and SQL
- Java and JavaScript

Question 6 of 10

Which of the following analytical and statistical techniques do data scientists commonly use?

- Classification
- Regression
- Clustering
- All of the above

Question 7 of 10

In machine learning, what is the primary difference between supervised and unsupervised learning?

- Supervised learning involves data that has been labeled and classified, while unsupervised learning data is unlabeled and unclassified.
- Supervised learning is monitored closely by data scientists, while they don't play a role in unsupervised learning.
- Supervised learning is only used for image recognition, while unsupervised learning can be used for various analytics applications.

Question 8 of 10

True or false? Bias is a common problem in data science applications.

- True
- False

Question 9 of 10

Why is data sampling useful for data scientists?

- It lets them analyze data sets in small batches to reduce their use of system resources.
- It reduces the amount of data storage space that's required for data science applications.
- It enables them to use a representative subset of data to build accurate analytical models more quickly.

Question 10 of 10

What is a common maxim about data scientists?

- They spend 80% of their time finding and preparing data and 20% analyzing it.
- They spend 80% of their time analyzing data and 20% finding and preparing it.

- They spend 80% of their time on failed analytics projects and 20% doing useful work.

Tool 2: Learning analytics

2.1. Please, explain whether you analyse your learning. Give some reasons.

2.2. What are benefits of learning analytics?

2.3. Please, take part in quiz developed by AnalyzingData357 (2025).

Q1. Learning Analytics is a process of collecting, analysing, measuring & _____ of data.

- Evaluating
- Developing understanding
- Reporting
- Optimising

Q2. Which of the following tools provide Learning Analytics?

- Doodle Analyst
- Kaneva Analytics
- Noco-Analyst
- Moodle

Q3. Which of the following predict student dropouts?

- Demographics
- Involvement
- Performance

- All options

Q4. Which of the following is a high-relevance factor for predicting student achievements?

- Academic Performance
- Discipline History
- Administrative information
- Background information

Q5. Please arrange the sequence of the learning analytics value chain in the correct order?

- Data, insight, decision
- Insight, data, decision
- Decision, data, insight
- Decision, insight, data

Q6. What is the most important element in adopting / integrating Learning Analytics practices?

- Technology & Tools
- People
- Data
- Frameworks

Q7. What is the logical order of (Learning) Analytics actions?

- Descriptive, diagnostic, predictive, prescriptive
- Diagnostic, descriptive, prescriptive predictive
- Diagnostic, descriptive, predictive, prescriptive
- Descriptive, diagnostic, prescriptive predictive

Q8. Is the use of data, statistical algorithms and machine learning techniques to identify the likelihood of future outcomes based on historical data.?

- Prescriptive analytics
- Predictive analytics
- Descriptive analytics
- Diagnostic analytics

Q9. Is an approach to analysis that can help you make decisions.

- Navies Bayes
- Neural network
- Decision tree
- Random forest

Q10. Is a statistical method that analyzes and finds relationships between two variables.

- Deep learning
- Neural network
- Markov model
- Linear regression

Tool 3: Mathematical methods of statistics

3.1. What is the role of mathematics in statistics?

3.2. What is the difference between descriptive and inferential statistics?

3.3. Please, match the term with the its definition as required in Table 7.

Table 7: Matching the term with its definition

Number	Term	Connecting number and letter of your choice	Letter	Definition
1	Mean		A	A position in a hierarchy or scale
2	Median		B	The average of a set of numbers, found by adding all numbers and dividing by the total count
3	Mode		C	The number that appears most frequently in a set of data
4	Ranking		D	The middle value in a set of numbers after they have been arranged in order

Correct answers: 1B, 2D, 3C and 4A.

Tool 4: Mathematical software

4.1. Please, describe your experience in the use of mathematical software: Have you used it? For what purposes? Was it friendly for users? Please, give some names.

4.2. What is the impact of the use of mathematical software on learners' STEM skills?

4.3. 1. Take part in Quiz developed by Ashebo (2025).

Q1: What does "MATLAB" stand for?

- a) Mathematical Analysis Tool for Linear Algebra and Beyond
 - b) Mathematical Algorithms and Theorems for Linear Behavior
 - c) Matrix Algebra Toolkit for Linear Equations
 - d) Matrix Laboratory
2. What is the result of $3 + 2 * 4$ in MATLAB?
- a) 14
 - b) 20
 - c) 11
 - d) 9
3. Which command is used to execute a MATLAB script from the command line?
- a) script
 - b) run
 - c) execute
 - d) load
4. Which MATLAB function is used to calculate the square root of a number?
- a) log
 - b) sqrt
 - c) power
 - d) exp
5. Given matrices A and B, which operation computes the element-wise product (of A and B)?

- a) $A .* B$
 - b) A / B
 - c) $A.^ B$
 - d) $A * B$
6. Which of the following is the correct way to define a row vector in MATLAB?
- a) $v = [1\ 2; 3]$
 - b) $v = [1, 2, 3]$
 - c) $v = [1\ 2\ 3]$
 - d) $v = [1; 2; 3]$
7. Given a matrix $A = [1\ 2; 3\ 4; 5\ 6]$, what is the value of $A(2, 1)$?
8. Which command clears the command window?
- a) clear
 - b) clc
 - c) reset
 - d) close all
9. Which command enables a title for the x-axis?
- a) horilabel()
 - b) xlabel()
 - c) xlabel[]
 - d) no command
10. What is the nature of the arrangement of the coefficients to store the following expression in MATLAB? $y = 3x^5 + x^2 + 6$

Answer: _____

Observations

STEM modules intend to have a positive impact on STEM learners, and, consequently, to foster quality STEM education for our common sustainable future.

STEM modules offers a coupling effect on our common sustainable development and greener future:

- On the one hand, STEM modules support the constant improvement of STEM learners' skills, while STEM skills are the cornerstone for the development of the world in a sustainable manner,
- On the other hand, STEM modules ensure a green or, in other words, digital way for the delivery of STEM education while green and digital are considered as the two sides of the same coin. Without digitalisation, climate neutrality and, therefore, sustainability cannot be achieved.

STEM modules' content is not static, it is permanently renewed and jointly built in cooperation with other STEM education participants (Zašcerinska, 2011). The proposed STEM modules offer modern teaching content for quality STEM education that can be used by teachers, learners, parents, enterprises and other interested stakeholders for STEM teaching and learning (Zascerinska, Emet, Usca, & Bikova, 2023).

Appropriate implementation of STEM modules powered by STEM platforms, artificial intelligence and integrated with learning analytics positively influences the development of STEM skills, spark learners' interest in STEM disciplines, and contribute to enhanced learning achievements and knowledge (Batuchina, Melnikova, Zascerinska, & Ahrens, 2023).

STEM modules' implementation promotes STEM learners' knowledge update as well as positive attitude to STEM education being the catalyst of choosing a STEM career. More chosen STEM careers will substantially support sustainable development of the globalised world.

Practical implications on STEM modules suggest that the proposed module duration may not coincide with the planned time. Module duration depends on learners' individual abilities and their level of education (e.g. school, vocational, adult, higher, professional development, etc.) as well as cultural traditions in education in his/her country.

The choice of topics can be also adjusted as new knowledge is ever appearing. Module content might be adapted to learners' educational level, his/her learning abilities to obtain new skills, and STEM education requirements in a specific country.

Teaching methodology, based on emotional cognition, for the implementation of the proposed STEM module content can be integrated into traditional teaching schemes, such as teaching and learning process, or introduced into novel teaching methods, e.g. use of Artificial Intelligence (AI).

Each individual tool developed in the proposed STEM modules is of interdisciplinary nature. Therefore, tools can be easily transferred from one STEM module to another.

Overall, the presented STEM modules facilitate quality STEM education. These STEM modules intend to ease STEM learners' integration into the labour market, therefore contributing to the growth of individuals' welfare and their closer social inclusion for our better and greener future (Zascerinska, Emet, Usca, & Bikova, 2023).

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Project Contact Information

Nordplus Project Database:

<https://espresso.projects.hkdir.no/nordplus?0&lang=en>

Project website:

<https://stemify.eu>

Project Facebook:

<https://www.facebook.com/stemifyyourclassroom/>

EPALE Platform:

<https://epale.ec.europa.eu/en/content/time-management-well-being-through-work-life-balance-sense-time>

ResearchGate:

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